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Physical Distribution Management And Performance Of Table Water Firms In Anambra State

EZEUDU, Anulika & MADUKA, Chinedu Okechukwu

**Department Of Marketing,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effect of physical distribution management on the performance of table water firms in Anambra State. The specific objectives of the study include: to determine the effect of transportation on performance of table water firms; to ascertain the effect of warehousing on performance of table water firms; to examine the effect of inventory management and control on performance of table water firms; to determine the effect of product packaging on performance of table water firms; and to ascertain the effect of strategic distribution planning on performance of table water firms. The study reviewed conceptual, theoretical and empirical literatures related to the study. The study was anchored on system theory. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population for this study comprised of four hundred and eleven (411) employees of fifteen selected table water companies in Anambra State. The entire population was studied because it is small and manageable. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. Frequency tables and percentages were employed in arranging and analyzing the data, while the hypotheses were tested using multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that transportation has significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. Warehousing was found to have significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. The study also found that inventory management and control have significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. The study further found that packaging of products has significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. Finally, the study found that strategic distribution planning has significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. The study concluded that physical distribution management has significant effect on the performance of table water firms in Anambra State. The study recommended that effective and efficient monitoring of the activities of the distributors; better internal information system; automation of inventory management practices; and paying proper attention to good packaging.

Keywords: Physical Distribution Management, Performance

INTRODUCTION

Distribution has been an important part of industrial and economic development for many years, but its effect has only been recognized in relative recent past (Somuyiwa, 2010). It is not easy to determine which of the many definitions is most suitable for distribution in that it is basically concerned with the efficient transfer of goods from the place of manufacture, to the place of consumption, in cost effective way whilst providing an acceptable service to the customer (Rushton, Croucher & Baker, 2006). Distribution can thus be described as a service that adds value to products by making them available at the

right time, in the right place, which provides an interface with the customer (Omur & Fahriye, 2016). However, economic transformation, and indeed, the development of any country are hardly possible without an efficient transport system. This is because goods should be transported from origin to specific destination via a specific route through a specific mode and for a specific purpose (Omondi, 2017). In essence, the ability to ensure accurate delivery of a product and raw materials, especially over long have necessitated the concept of transportation into distribution systems.

The distribution logistics system is responsible for actual movement of products in such a way as to accomplish the goal of providing time and place utility. Distribution logistic management according to Armstrong and Kotler (2009) involves planning, implementing and controlling of the physical flow of materials, final goods and related information from points of origin to points of consumption to meet customer requirements at a profit. Distribution logistics management is the planning, implementation and control of the processes involved in the flow and storage of materials from the point of origin (as raw materials) through the various value added stages to the point of consumption (as finished goods) [The Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (CSCMP) (2011)]. Succinctly stated, they involve getting the right product in the right quantity to the right customer in the right place at the right time in the right condition and at the right cost. The distribution logistic system ensures that all transporting, storing and product-handling activities of a business and a whole channel system are coordinated as one system that seeks to minimize the total cost of distribution for a given customer service level, (Perreault, Cannon & McCarthy, 2010).

Distribution logistic management primarily is moving goods from origin to destination. Marketing strategy planning is based on meeting customers' needs better than the competitors. It seeks to create a differential advantage within target segments by which a distinct competitive position relative to other companies can be established and from which profit flows. Delivering the right goods to the buyers at the right time and at the lowest possible cost is an important aspect of every good marketing program (Ewuzie, 2014). Distribution logistics provides the means by which the product can reach the customer or end user timely, in the appropriate condition and required location. Moving and storing materials and goods throughout the distribution network require that physical distribution managers make decisions about facilities, inventory, transportation, communications and materials handling and packaging.

Many business organizations have come short of achieving their desired goals and objectives even after producing high quality products. These shortcomings have been attributed to improper, ineffective and inefficient strategies as it relates to distribution of goods. The purpose of distribution logistic management is to make goods to be physically available to the ultimate consumer at reasonable prices. It is therefore; very imperative that the products are distributed in the most efficient manner to reach the ultimate consumer whose patronage ensures the survival of the organization. By so doing, the organization will enjoy consistent high sales turnover and subsequently high profit delivery (Ukwueze, 2007).

Today, companies are faced with choice of distribution path or strategy that will make product readily available to potential customers (Achumba, 2000). Kotler (1996) stated that distribution logistic management comprises of the tasks involved in planning, implementing, and control of the physical flow of material and final goods from the point of origin to the point of use to meet the needs of consumers at a profit. He also reveals that many companies state their distribution logistic objectives as getting the right goods, to the right place, at the right time, for least possible costs, hence decisions must be made to achieve the objectives. The starting point for designing distribution logistic management is to study what the competitors are offering and the needs of the customers are interrelated including the time of delivery. Therefore, this study examined physical distribution management and marketing performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

It can be argued that distribution logistic management has impacted greatly in ensuring that goods and services are made available when and where they are desired and in safe conditions. However, due to the rise in technological development and global marketing, the process is not without problems as many

companies and business people still lack adequate distribution facilities leading to the spoilage of these products before getting to their destination points (Kahia & Iravo, 2014).

The rate of technological innovation and fluctuation in consumer demand are among the factors that have increased the dynamism of the competitive environment to which organizations must respond. Inadequate distribution logistics expertise, inadequate distribution infrastructure, combined with unskilled manpower can be blamed for the great loss and damage of goods experienced, especially for perishable products. The challenges however, create opportunities for companies with advanced distribution systems and skilled employees, efficient and effective management to grow their market. In addition, Oladun (2012) identified administrative bottlenecks in the collection and handling of products, unnecessary hoarding of products, inadequate storage facility, numerous and unnecessary middle men, problem of processing and packaging and insecurity on the Nigerian roads as the problems militating against distribution of products in Nigeria. Also, inventory problem can occur. Many problems can occur with inventories including stock-outs, incorrect inventory mix and excess inventory. Inventory problems involve too much or not enough items in stock. Too much stock lead to excess expenses in carrying inventory and too little creates customer dissatisfaction. Warehousing operations problems include damaging products when stocking and loading, incorrectly filling customer's orders, theft and incurring excessive costs in performing warehouse functions. Transportation and delivery operations problems may occur when goods are transported from producer to ultimate consumer. Problem may occur because of delay, damage, theft and high transport cost (Ewuzie, 2014).

El-Ruphia (2000) pointed out that the inefficiency in the distribution of goods and services in Nigeria is as a result of lack of clear-cut policy on physical distribution channels. He further noted that the majority of middlemen in our society are untrained and consist mainly of men and women who because of their financial position and or their connections are assigned distributorship of products. These problems have adversely affected the management, marketing, distribution and productivity of enterprises in the country. The Nigeria sachet water industries distribution logistic system is besieged with problems. These problems manifest mostly in transportation, warehousing, and inventory management leaving them unable to meet the demand of their customers. The continuous increase in the cost of transportation due to poor nature of our roads, high cost of vehicles and spare parts pose a serious problem to an effective coverage of territories in the distribution both in rural and urban areas in the country. Therefore this study sought to examined physical distribution management and marketing performance of table water companies in Anambra State.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of physical distribution management on marketing performance of table water firms in Anambra State. The specific objectives include to:

1. Determine the effect of transportation on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.
2. Ascertain the effect of warehousing on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.
3. Examine the effect of inventory management on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.
4. Determine the effect of packaging on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.
5. Ascertain the effect of strategic distribution planning on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study.

1. To what extent does transportation affect performance of table water firms in Anambra State significant?
2. To what extent does warehousing affect performance of table water firms in Anambra State significant?
3. To what extent does inventory management affect performance of table water firms in Anambra State significant?
4. To what extent does packaging affect performance of table water firms in Anambra State significant?

5. To what extent does strategic distribution planning affect performance of table water firms in Anambra State significant?

Hypotheses

The following tentative statements stated in null were formulated to guide this study.

Ho₁: Transportation has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Ho₂: Warehousing has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Ho₃: Inventory management has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Ho₄: Packaging has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Ho₅: Strategic distribution planning has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Physical Distribution Management

Physical distribution management is coordination of the information and goods flow among the involved parties of the channel, so that the goods are available in the right places, at the right time, in the right quantities, and in a cost-efficient manner (Ferrell & Hartline 2011). It involves not only physical movement of goods (transportation), but also location of plants, warehousing (storage), inventory quantities, etc. (Cateora & Graham 2007). With an effectively organized distribution logistic system, a company can optimize its transportation costs, levels of inventory, volumes of production, and labour force (Cateora & Graham 2007). Physical distribution management refers to the management of the flow of procedures from the products from the production points to the consumption points. According to the American Council of Physical Distribution Management cited in Ukwueze (2007), Physical distribution management is a term employed in manufacturing and commerce to describe the broad range of activities concerned with efficient movement of finished products from the end of the production line to the beginning of the production lime. These activities include foresight, transportation, warehousing, material handling, material handling, protective packaging, inventory control, plant and warehouse site section, order processing market forecasting and customer services (Ehikwe, 2002).

Kotler and Armstrong (2001) see physical distribution management as the task involved in planning, implementing and controlling the physical flow of materials, final goods and related information from point of origin to points of consumption to meet customer requirements at a profit. Rushton, Croucher and Baker (2006) noted that physical distribution management involves the handling and moving of raw materials and finished products from producer to consumers, often an intermediary. Its objective is to put the product within an arm's length of desire. By administering its physical flow from the organization to the customers at the time and place where they want them at a reasonable cost. So, physical distribution management is the process of strategically managing the movement and storage of materials, parts and finished inventory form suppliers, between enterprise facilities and to customers. Physical distribution management objective as getting the right goods, to the right places, at the right time, for the least cost. In essence, physical distribution is the science of business logistics whereby the proper amount of the right kind of product is made available at the place where demand for it exists at the time it exists. Viewed in this light, distribution logistic management is the key link between manufacturing and demand creation.

Physical distribution management is a whole process that concern also materials and finished product, a physical (spacial) movement of goods from the manufacturers to intermediaries and finally to the ultimate consumer. Distribution accomplishes this by providing time and place utility, in other words, availability and its goals are like any other marketing goals: consumer's satisfaction and profit for the firms (Muhscina, 2008). There are various routes that products or services use after their production until they are purchased and used by end users. These channels are referred to as distribution channels or marketing channels. Therefore, distribution channels are all those organizations that a product has to go through between its production and consumption (Kotler et al, 2006).

Transportation

Transportation is one of the most visible elements of logistics operations. The transportation system is the physical link connecting a company's customers, raw materials suppliers, plants, warehouses and channel members, all of which represent the fixed points in a logistics supply chain. The fixed points in the logistics system are where some activities temporarily halt the flow of goods in the logistics pipeline. Consequently, the transportation carriers used to connect these facilities affect not only the transportation cost but also the operating costs of the facilities and the prices paid by the ultimate users of the products (Uzel, 2018). Transportation is responsible for the physical movement or flow of materials and goods in the supply chain. The logistics or physical distribution manager is responsible for selecting the modes of transportation used in moving the raw materials and finished goods or for developing private transportation as an alternative (Ewuzie, 2014).

Warehousing

Omondi (2017) indicated that warehousing includes all activities between inbound logistics from suppliers and outbound logistics to outlets, especially picking outlet-specific orders. Warehousing refers to the storing and assorting products in order to create time utility. The basic purpose of the warehousing activity is to arrange placement of goods, provide storage facility to store them, consolidate them with other similar products, divide them into smaller quantities and build up assortment of products. Generally, larger the number of warehouses a firm has the lesser would be the time taken in serving customers at different locations, but greater would be the cost of warehousing. Thus, the firm has to strike a balance between the cost of warehousing and the level of customer service (Omur & Fahriye, 2016).

Inventory Management

Inventory management plays a significant role in physical distribution of products. Inventory management therefore has been defined in many ways by many authors. As expected, these authors defined inventory management based on their perception of the subject matter. Inventory management is a management cum operations function. It requires operational processes to be followed and maintained on the floor and in inventory management systems. Coupled with operations, it entails continuous study; analysis and decision making to control and manage inventory levels (Obiri-Yeboah, Ackah & Makafui, 2015). Ogbo, Onekanma and Ukpere (2015) defines inventory control as a process of ensuring that the right quality of the relevant stock is available at the right time and in the right place. Omar (2016) on his own part defines inventory control as the means of ensuring that actual flow of inventory in an organization conforms with plan. Generally, inventory control, as a management tool, is the method or methods employed in maintaining detailed lists, showing quantities and values of raw materials, work - in - process, and finished goods held in warehouse stock (Oliomogbe, 2002). Tungo (2014) see inventory management as a process of efficiently overseeing the constant flow of units into and out of an existing inventory. This process usually involves controlling the transfer of units in order to prevent the inventory from becoming too high, or dwindling to levels that could put the operation for the company into jeopardy. Inventory management is the overseeing and controlling of the ordering, storage and use of components that a company will use in the production of the items it will sell as well as the overseeing and controlling of quantities of finished products for sale. Business's inventory is one of its major assets and represents an investment that is tied up until the items is sold or used in the production of an item that is sold. It also costs money to store, track and insure inventory (Onchoke & Wanyoike, 2016).

Strategic Distribution Planning

Sodhi (2003) posit that strategic distribution planning includes the determination and redesigning of the physical distribution structures between warehouses and outlets, the flexibility and degree of a supplier's own outbound supply chain activities. Strategic distribution planning creates structures for the transportation modes for direct links to stores, warehouse-to-store deliveries and cross-docking operations.

Often, retailers use a distribution mix depending on supplier location and product characteristics. They use their warehouses for storage and picking, but sometimes they additionally serve for cross-docking (Lambert, 2006). Another important function of strategic distribution planning is to regulate to what

extent the retailer should handle the outbound logistics, and how strategic partnerships with service providers are arranged. This enables the firm to effectively integrate its functions and activities with its supply chain providers and thus improve supply chain performance (Kaipia, 2008).

Packaging

Packaging is a very important aspect of physical distribution. Onah and Thomas (2004) defined packaging as the use of container, components, plus decoration or labels to protect, contain, identify and facilitate the use of products. It is containment and packaging prior to sales with the primary purpose of facilitating the use of products. The container or wrappers is called package. The package include up to three levels of materials: the primary which is the immediate container; the secondary is referred to packaging necessary to protect the primary package; and the third is shipping packaging which referred to packaging necessary for storage. Kotler (2006) defines packaging as "all the activities of designing and producing the container for a product." Packaging can be define as the wrapping material around a consumer item that serves to contain, identify, describe, protect, display, promote, and otherwise make the product marketable and keep it clean. Deliya and Parmar (2012) defined as an extrinsic element of the product. Packaging is the container for a product. Development of wrappers and covers, for company's offerings is known as Packaging (Keller, 2009). Panwar (2004) see packaging as the act of containing, protecting and presenting the contents through the long chain of production, handling and transportation to their destinations in as good a state, as they were, at the time of production. Packaging is an important part of the branding process as it plays a role in communicating the image and identity of a company (Sajuyigbe, et. el., 2013).

Performance

Conceptualizing marketing performance have been a difficult issue. It is somewhat surprising that a review of the literature has failed to unearth a clear and explicit definition of the term 'marketing performance', even though research on marketing performance is well established (AMA 1959). Bonoma and Clark (2008) note that: "...perhaps no other concept in marketing's short history has proven as stubbornly resistant to conceptualization, definition, or application as that of marketing performance...". The only consensus that has been reached in both the strategic (Morgan & Strong 2003) and marketing literature (Morgan, Clark, & Gooner 2002; Vorhies & Morgan 2003) is that marketing performance is multidimensional in nature. However, that which constitutes a superior marketing performance may differ between businesses (Vorhies & Morgan 2003). The effectiveness and efficiency dimensions of performance may not converge and may even be inversely related in the short term, firms tend to make important decisions that reflect a trade-off between emphasising either effectiveness or efficiency in the setting of their marketing goals and allocation of resources.

Following on the approach used by Homburg (2007), marketing performance is herein defined as: "...the effectiveness and efficiency of an organization's marketing activities with regard to market-related goals, such as revenues, growth, and market share...". Ambler (2000) also points out a lack of precision in the terminology used to describe marketing performance. He proposes the adoption of the word 'metric' to capture a top-level measure of marketing performance (Shaw & White 2009). Ambler (2000) provides a detailed explanation of marketing metrics: "A 'metric' is a performance measure that top management should review. It is a measure that matters to the whole business. The term comes from music and implies regularity: the reviews should typically take place yearly or half yearly. A metric is not just another word for measure – while all metrics are measures, not all measures are metrics. Metrics should be necessary, precise, consistent and sufficient (i.e. comprehensive) for review purposes. Metrics may be financial (usually from the profit and loss account), from the marketplace, or from non-financial internal sources (innovation and employee).

Theoretical Framework

This research work is anchored on system theory. Systems theory was proposed in the 1940's by the biologist Ludwig von Bertalanffy. Therefore, this theory has been applied in several disciplines. The theory emphasized that real systems are open to, and interact with, their environments, systems theory focuses on the arrangement of and relations between the parts which connect them into a whole. This

particular organization determines a system, which is independent of the concrete substance of the elements.

Organization as a system refers to a set of elements or units, which interacts with its environment by importing inputs, while it exports outputs. A system can be closed or open. An open system interacts with its environment and closed systems do not. Agu (2007) stresses further that demands are made from the environment on the system in form of inputs, for example, demands of the citizens for the maintenance of law and order and provision of infrastructural facilities. These demands are then processed into outputs, which are authoritative decisions within the governmental administration. The feedback corrects the actions of the administrative system. This is necessary for equilibrium.

System's theory is a conceptual framework and methodology for understanding the operation of a system where there are two or several actors that are essentially components of the whole. Systems theory is therefore defined as a series of statements about the relationship among independent variables in which changes in one variable is accompanied or followed by changes in other variables. In a functional democracy, the application of the system theory cannot be over emphasized. This is because it addresses the issues of interdependence, dependence and interactions of variables.

Physical distribution can be viewed as a system of components linked together for the efficient movement of products. Using a system approach to describe physical distribution, the components include; customer service, transportation, warehousing, order processing, inventory control, protective packaging and materials handling. These components are interrelated, hence: decisions made in one area affect the relative efficiency of others. For example, a small business that provides customised personal computers may transport finished products by air rather than by truck, as faster delivery times may allow lower inventory costs, which would more than offset the higher cost of air transport. Viewing physical distribution from a system's perspective can be the key to providing a defined level of customer service at the lowest possible cost.

Empirical Review

Many scholars and researchers have examined distribution logistic management and its impact on marketing performance. Ewuzie (2014) examined the relationship between physical distribution and customer satisfaction in Nigerian Bottling Company Plc, Enugu State. Frequency, percentage, means, standard deviation and Pearson correlation were used for data analysis. The study found out among others that there is a significant relationship between performance of physical distribution service activities (transportation, warehousing, inventory control and order processing) and physical distribution service (product availability, PDS timeliness, PDS quality, PDS flexibility). And it was also found out that Physical distribution service has significant relationship with overall customer satisfaction. The study then concludes that as performance of physical distribution service activities becomes more effective and efficient in the industry, it would lead to improvement of physical distribution service which will in turn transcend to overall customer satisfaction.

Okeudo (2013) carried out a research on the optimization of physical distribution of consumer goods in Nigeria using Unilever Nigeria Plc (South-East Region) as a case study. The sampling frame of the research consists of a very large population which consists of all warehouse and Unilever retailers in South-east, Nigeria. A total of 107 questionnaires were dispatched to the retailers in the two locations selected. A total of 101 questionnaires were returned 50 from Onitsha location and 51 from Owerri location. The study found that physical distribution has significant impact on marketing performance in Unilever Nigeria Plc.

Okeudo and Chikwendu (2013) carried out a correlational analysis of distribution cost and freight characteristics of manufactured goods in Unilever Nigeria Plc. Data was collected by the administration of questionnaire to a total of 107 respondents of two major plants of Unilever Nigeria Plc in the South East zone of Nigeria. Analysis was carried out on the data collected using a regression and correlation to establish the statistical relationship between the dependent variable (distribution cost) and the independent variables (weight of the goods and the quantity of the goods) respectively. A positive correlation coefficient(r) value of 0.983 was discovered, indicating a high positive relationship between the variable

was discovered. Obviously, an increase in the quantity or weight of the goods must lead to an increased cost of distribution.

Ukwueze (2007) appraised the distribution strategies of production companies using Nigerian Bottling Company Plc, Enugu as a reference point. A sample size of 240 respondents was randomly selected from the Staff, Management and Customers of the Nigerian Bottling Company Plc in Enugu. Both primary and secondary data were collected and analysed using the chi-square test. The study revealed that the various distribution strategies used by NBC Plc for tackling distribution problems include multiple distribution, selective distribution and extensive distribution strategies. The study also found that physical distribution policies of NBC Plc have encouraged their consumers' loyalty; and that the NBC Plc chosen channels of physical distribution have made impact on the consumer patronage.

Kahia and Iravo (2014) examined the factors affecting the performance of distribution logistics among production firms in Kenya. The research was carried out in Bata Shoe Company Kenya limited where questionnaires were used to collect primary data to determine whether there are factors that affect the performance of distribution logistics. The data collected was then analysed and presented in frequency distribution tables. The study found that the customer, the product, technology and distribution structure are all factors that affect the performance of distribution logistics. The study also found that customers' location, ordered quantities, customer requirements and the number of customers are all customer aspects that affect the performance of distribution logistics.

Obaji (2011) examined the effects of channels of distribution on Nigerian product sales. The quantitative research method was the instrument used to collect data for the study. A total of 300 copies of the questionnaires were distributed to sampled consumers, distributors and marketing staff of the company, out of which 200 copies was retrieved back. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 15 and the t-Test statistical tool was employed to test the significance between the observed variables and the underlying construct. The findings revealed that the involvement of channels of distribution affects sales of product and that consumers prefer to buy from intermediaries than from producer channels.

Mbondo, Okibo and Mogwambo (2015) examined the influence of physical distribution strategies on the performance of service firms in Kenya with particular interest on Print Media Industry. The study adopted a survey design. The target population was 53 respondents selected using Census sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was used. Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics which involved the use of percentages and frequency tables. The findings were: customer service strategy and transport logistics strategy were the major physical distribution strategies adopted; this result showed that their use in the industry was of high significance in contributing towards performance of the print media industry; a strong and positive correlation existed between physical distribution strategies and performance of the print media industry.

Ilodigwe (2011) assessed the effectiveness of the distribution strategies of A-Z Petroleum Products Ltd. The population of this study was the management staff of A-Z petroleum products Ltd and the company's distributors in Aba metropolis. The researcher collected data from both primary and secondary source.. Stratified sampling technique was used for larger sample of the study. The statistical technique used to test the hypothesis was chi-square at 5% level of significance. The researcher discovered that the cost of transportation significantly affect the price of A-Z lubricant because the firm bears the cost of transportation right from the source of raw materials (additives) to the point of delivery to distributor warehouse. The researcher also discovered that bad road network significantly affect the demand of A-Z lubricants in Aba metropolis because some of the customers cum potential customers that suppose to buy from Aba moved to other neighboring towns like Port Harcourt, Uyo, Owerri to buy due to the bad road network currently experiencing in Aba.

Omur and Fahriye (2016) examined physical distribution flexibility in logistics systems and its impact on productivity. To measure the effect of distribution flexibility, a basic model is developed according to the literature survey. Simple questionnaires are developed and asked to the customers of the courier firms to identify the competitive advantage points for the customers and rank the different firms on the business.

Customers are asked to evaluate the three properties of the logistics flexibility for each company. The data generated were analyzed using descriptive statistics and chi-square test. Physical supply flexibility, physical distribution flexibility and demand management flexibility were found as the indicators of the physical distribution flexibility. The study also found that physical distribution flexibility has significant impact on productivity.

Mukolwe and Wanyoike (2015) carried out an assessment on the effect of logistics management practices on operational efficiency at Mumias Sugar Company Limited, Kenya. The target population for the study included staff from selected departments of Mumias Sugar Company, representatives of farmers, and officials from the Ministry of Agriculture and the Kenya Sugar board. Stratified sampling technique was used to select the predetermined sample size of 92. Purposive and convenience sampling methods were used to select sample elements for interviews. Data was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and inferentially through correlation and regression analysis. The study revealed that effective management of information flow improves the company's internal and external processes. Automation of warehousing activities greatly enhances accuracy, speed of operations and reduces wastage. Transport management and physical distribution practices on the other hand allows faster and cost effective flow of goods and raw materials thus improving operational efficiency

Gap in Literature

Existing empirical literatures revealed conflicting empirical findings showing that the relationship between physical distribution management and marketing performance is not yet resolved. For instance Mbondo, Okibo and Mogwambo (2015) found a strong and positive correlation existed between physical distribution strategies and performance. Omur and Fahriye (2016) found that physical distribution has significant impact on productivity. Green, Whitten and Inman (2008) found that logistics performance and supply chain management strategy positively impact marketing and financial performance. On the contrary, Obun (2012) found that ineffective and high cost of transportation, lack of storage facilities and basic infrastructure hindered the marketing performance of agricultural products. Also, majority of the studies were done in environment outside Anambra State and none of these studies covered table water sector, hence revealing a knowledge gap. This study bridged this gap by using a more robust methodology and by using a wide data set.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey research design was used in carrying out this research. The study was carried out in Anambra State. Anambra State has three senatorial zone namely Anambra Central, Anambra South and Anambra North. Only the employees of table water manufacturing companies were sampled for the study. The population for this study comprised all the employees of fifteen selected table water companies in Anambra State. The population of the study is the four hundred and eleven (411) employees of the selected table water. Since the population of the study is small and manageable, the researcher decided to make use of the entire population as the sample size. Hence, the sample size for the study is four hundred and eleven (411) employees. Questionnaire was employed as the instrument of data collection. Multiple regression analysis was employed to test the hypotheses formulated exclusively for this study. The regression model is represented as:

$$MP = \alpha + \beta_1 TL + \beta_2 WL + \beta_3 IMC + \beta_4 PP + \beta_5 SDP + \epsilon$$

Where:

MP =Marketing Performance

TL = Transportation Logistics

WL = Warehousing logistics

IMC = Inventory Management and Control

PP = Product Packaging

SDP = Strategic Distribution Planning

α = Constant Term

β = Beta coefficients

ϵ = Error Term

RESULTS

Multiple regression technique was employed to test the effect of physical distribution management on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. The result is presented in the tables below.

Table 1 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.867 ^a	.752	.675	3.703	2.174

a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic Distribution Planning , Product Packaging , Inventory Management and Control , Warehousing, Transportation

b. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance

Source: SPSS 21.0

Table 1 shows the model summary which indicates the R Square, Adjusted R Square and Durbin-Watson. The R² value of 0.752 indicates that indicates that 75.2% variation in performance of table water firms in Anambra State were accounted by the combined variations in strategic distribution planning, product packaging, inventory management and control, warehousing logistics and transportation logistics. The adjusted R² value of 67.5% indicates similar trends. This implies that distribution logistic management account for significant variations (67.5%) in performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Durbin-Watson statistics checks for the presence or otherwise of autocorrelation in the regression model in order to determine its reliability for economic predictions. The Durbin-Watson statistics of 2.174 in the table1 above indicates that the variables in the model are not autocorrelated and therefore are reliable for predictions.

Table 2 Analysis of Variance for the Model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	148.436	5	29.687	2.165	.037 ^a
	Residual	5169.768	377	13.713		
	Total	5318.204	382			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Strategic Distribution Planning , Product Packaging , Inventory Management and Control , Warehousing, Transportation

b. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance

Source: SPSS 21.0

Table 2 indicates that the regression model recorded f-statistics value of 2.165 and probability value of 0.037 signifying that the independent variables have significant relationship with the dependent variable. This shows that distribution logistic management proxied by strategic distribution planning, product packaging, inventory management and control, warehousing and transportation can collectively explain the variations in performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

The hypotheses formulated in this study were empirically tested to determine the significance or otherwise of the tentative statements. The t-statistics value and probability value were employed the testing the hypotheses and the result is presented in table 3 below:

Table 3 Regression Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	19.310	2.085		9.262	.000
Transportation	.020	.047	.022	4.428	.000
Warehousing	.028	.050	.029	2.557	.003
Inventory Management and Control	.082	.049	.086	2.686	.001
Product Packaging	.125	.051	.127	2.462	.014
Strategic Distribution Planning	.044	.050	.044	3.874	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Marketing Performance

Source: SPSS 21.0

Hypothesis One

Ho: Transportation has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. Transportation has a t-statistics of 4.428 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that transportation has a significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: Warehousing has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. Warehousing has a t-statistics of 2.557 and a probability value of 0.003 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that warehousing has a significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three

Ho: Inventory management has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Inventory management has a t-statistics 2.686 and a probability value of 0.001 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that inventory management has a significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Four

Ho: Packaging has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. Packaging has a t-statistics 2.462 and a probability value of 0.014 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that packaging has significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Five

Ho: Strategic distribution planning has no significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

Strategic distribution planning has a t-statistics 3.874 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that strategic distribution planning has a significant effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This study investigated the effect of physical distribution management on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. Data sourced from the employees of table water firms in Anambra State were subjected to empirical analysis and the following became evident. The study found that transportation has a significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. This agrees with the findings of Uzel (2018) that physical distribution practices have significant positive effect on the performance. This also agrees with the findings of Kuswanto, Mohd, Radiah and Hamidreza (2012) that transportation coordination had positive and significant relationships with firm performance.

Warehousing was found to have significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. This agrees with the findings of Okeudo (2013) that physical distribution has significant impact on marketing performance. This also agrees with the findings of Abutu (2014) that warehousing have significant impact on distribution effectiveness..

The study also found that inventory management have significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. This collaborates the findings of Abutu (2014) that inventory management have significant impact on distribution effectiveness. This also agrees with the findings of Omondi (2017) that stock control influence organizational productivity.

The study further found that packaging of products have significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. This agrees with the findings of Kuswanto, Mohd, Radiah and Hamidreza (2012) that packaging had positive and significant relationships with firm performance.

Finally, the study found that strategic distribution planning have significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. This agrees with the findings of Omondi (2017) that that distribution planning influence organizational productivity.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the effect of physical distribution management on performance of table water firms in Anambra State. The study found that transportation has a significant effect on performance of table water firms. The study also found that warehousing has a significant effect on marketing performance of table water. Furthermore, inventory management was found to have significant effect on performance of table water firms. Packaging was found to have significant effect on performance of table water firms. Finally, strategic distribution planning has significant effect on performance of table water firms. Based on the foregoing, the study concludes that physical distribution management has significant positive effect on performance of table water firms in Anambra State.

RECOMMENDATION

The study recommends the following:

1. The company should device a more effective and efficient way of monitoring the activities of their distributors and should establish more depots to allow for direct dealings with the consumers.
2. Better internal information system should be developed in the warehousing system so as to effectively convey the information on real time basis within the firm especially when these warehouses are operated on decentralized basis.
3. This study also recommends the automation of inventory management practices table water firms in Anambra State. Automation will help them in inventory control by setting inventory control levels and calculating the amount of inventory to hold and release therefore improving the marketing performance of table water firms.
4. It is highly recommended that table water firms should pay proper attention to good packaging. It is necessary to set the packaging standard and to implement strategy accordingly for better protection and promotion of their table water products. They should not sacrifice the strength and effectiveness of the product package for cost as the firm to gain immensely from them.
5. For effective and efficient distribution system to take place, there should be strategic distribution planning for all the departments concerned. Transport, sales, production, marketing and purchasing should all work as a team to plan how customers' can be satisfied best without bottlenecks in order to enhance marketing performance.

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